

Device Lifespan Prediction Through Predictive Machine Learning Model

This project is submitted to

St. Vincent Pallotti College of Engineering and Technology

(An Autonomous Institution Affiliated to Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University,
Nagpur)

*in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree
of Bachelor of Technology in*

Computer Science and Engineering (Data Science)

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CERTIFICATE

Certified that this project report on “**Device Lifespan Prediction Through Predictive Machine Learning Model**” is the bonafide work of **B.V.S. Chandrika, Pratik Manwatkar, Rose Manoj and Tejas Kasture** who carried out the project work under my supervision in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Bachelor of Technology in **Computer Science and Engineering (Data Science)** of **St. Vincent Pallotti College of Engineering Technology**,
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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This project work is one of the major milestones in my journey of learning. We would like to sincerely thank **Prof. Aashish R. Dandekar, project guide** for his guidance at every stage of the project and for his prompt and insightful input.

We would like to thank **Dr. Manish Gudadhe, Head, Department of Computer Science and Engineering (Data Science)** and all our faculty members who reviewed our work and pointed out the shortcomings, their valuable insights and recommendations propelled our project forward, helping us overcome challenges and complexities along the way. Also, we are very grateful to the Institute Management, Principal Dr. Vijay M Wadhai for their overwhelming support in providing us the facilities of the computer lab and other required infrastructure.

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ABSTRACT

This project, "Device Lifespan Prediction using Predictive ML Model," focuses on leveraging machine learning to predict the remaining lifespan of electronic devices. As e-waste continues to rise globally, predicting the longevity of devices can significantly contribute to sustainable consumption and responsible recycling. The website developed in this project offers two key features: predicting the lifespan of a user's device and collecting survey data to improve future predictions.

The Prediction Page allows users to input device details such as type, brand, model, and usage. Based on this information, a machine learning model predicts the device's remaining lifespan, which is displayed on a results page along with a confidence level. The Survey Page gathers additional data, including the number of years a device has lasted, and stores this information in a PostgreSQL database hosted on Supabase. This data is used to refine the prediction model, making it more accurate over time.

The prediction model, built using regression techniques, was trained on a combination of user survey data and publicly available datasets. While the current dataset is limited, it provides a foundation for ongoing improvement. The system does not collect personal user data but uses device-specific information to generate personalized predictions.

This project contributes to e-waste awareness by providing users with insights into the expected lifespan of their devices. It encourages responsible device maintenance and recycling practices. Future developments include incorporating advanced machine learning models, expanding the data sources, and adding features such as real-time device health monitoring via IoT. The system has the potential to play a significant role in reducing e-waste by helping users make informed decisions about device usage and disposal.

Overall, this project demonstrates how machine learning can be applied to environmental issues, offering a tool for more sustainable technology use.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction of Project

The rapid growth of e-waste globally is a significant environmental concern. Electronic devices often have a shorter lifespan due to early disposal by consumers. This project develops a predictive machine learning model that estimates the lifespan of devices based on historical data, usage patterns, and brand information. The goal is to raise awareness about e-waste by providing accurate predictions of when devices might fail, enabling users to optimize their usage and make informed decisions about recycling and disposal.

1.2 Scope of Work

After development, the project will take various details about electronic devices as input and provide:

- An estimate of the potential e-waste based on the device's characteristics.
- A prediction of the device's lifespan using machine learning techniques.
- Educational content on e-waste management, like links to recycling centres and collection programs.

The project focuses primarily on common household devices such as smartphones, laptops, and tablets.

1.4 Operating Environment – Hardware and Software (Technology used)

- **Hardware:** The system will be developed and tested on standard desktop computer.
- **Software:**
 - **Backend:** Python, with libraries such as Pandas, NumPy, and Scikit-learn for data processing and machine learning.
 - **Frontend:** Flask framework to develop the web interface.
 - **Database:** Supabase for storing user data and device records in a PostgreSQL database.

CHAPTER 2: REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

The lifespan of electronic devices is influenced by numerous factors, including usage patterns, environmental conditions, and the inherent quality of the device components. Accurately predicting when a device will fail is a complex task, requiring the integration of various data sources and predictive models. This chapter reviews existing methodologies, tools, and approaches used for predicting device lifespans, with a particular focus on the application of predictive analytics and machine learning techniques. The review highlights the strengths and limitations of current models, and identifies gaps in the literature that this research aims to address, particularly in the context of personalized lifespan predictions and the role of e-waste management.

2.2 Overview of E-Waste

M. Khurram S. Bhutta, Adnan Omar, and Xiaozhe Yang: In their article, "Electronic Waste: A Growing Concern in Today's Environment", the authors address the escalating issue of electronic waste (e-waste) as a major environmental challenge. They explore how the surge in global consumption of electronic products, coupled with rapidly decreasing product life cycles, has led to an alarming increase in the volume of e waste. The authors highlight that many consumers, in their pursuit of the latest technologies, often replace functioning devices prematurely, exacerbating the problem. Moreover, they emphasize the detrimental effects of improper disposal methods such as landfilling and incineration, which release toxic substances like lead, mercury, and cadmium into the environment. These hazardous chemicals contribute to the contamination of soil, water, and air, posing serious health risks to humans and wildlife alike. The authors argue that without appropriate recycling measures or sustainable disposal practices, the problem of e-waste will continue to worsen, further burdening the environment. They call for increased awareness, policy intervention, and the development of more effective waste management strategies to mitigate the growing risks associated with e-waste

Lenny Halim and Yosephine Suharyanti: In their paper, "E-Waste: Current Research and Future Perspective on Developing Countries", the authors explore the growing problem of electronic waste, particularly in developing nations. They highlight how the rapid increase in discarded electronics, driven by technological advancements and consumer demand, is placing a disproportionate burden on these countries. The authors discuss the challenges faced in managing e-waste, including inadequate regulations, lack of recycling infrastructure, and the health risks posed by informal disposal practices.

Pankaj R. Kaushik and Sunil Herat: In their article, "Current State of e Waste Management in India", the authors examine the e-waste management landscape in India, one of the world's largest producers of electronic waste. The authors discuss how rapid industrialization, increasing consumer electronics demand, and short product lifespans have contributed to the growing e-waste problem in the country. They point out the challenges India faces, such as an underdeveloped formal recycling infrastructure, a thriving informal sector that processes e-waste unsafely, and inadequate enforcement of e-waste regulations. Kaushik and Herat suggest that while India has implemented e-waste management rules, gaps in implementation and lack of public awareness hinder their effectiveness. They propose that strengthening formal recycling systems, improving regulatory enforcement, and raising awareness about safe disposal practices are essential steps for sustainable e-waste management in India.

2.3 E-Waste Management and the Role of Predictive Analytics

Hatim Madkhali, Salahaldeen Duraib, Linh Nguyen, Mukesh Prasad, Manu Sharma, and Sudhanshu Joshi: In their article, “*A Comprehensive Review on E-Waste Management Strategies and Prediction Methods: A Saudi Arabia Perspective*”, Madkhali et al. explore the state of e-waste management in Saudi Arabia, highlighting the unique challenges the country faces due to rapid technological adoption, urbanization, and an increasing population. The authors emphasize that these factors have significantly contributed to the growing volume of electronic waste, exacerbating the environmental and health impacts.

The paper outlines the current e-waste management strategies in Saudi Arabia, discussing the role of formal and informal sectors in processing e-waste. While the government has initiated e-waste management programs, the authors argue that there is a significant gap in infrastructure, especially in the formal recycling sector. The informal sector continues to handle a large portion of e-waste, often using unsafe methods that pose serious risks to both human health and the environment.

Madkhali et al. also delve into the prediction methods used for forecasting e-waste generation and device lifespan, focusing on the role of predictive analytics and machine learning. They discuss how these methods can help in estimating the volume of e-waste generated, as well as predicting the end-of-life of electronic devices, which can significantly improve waste management strategies and recycling efforts.

The authors conclude by suggesting that Saudi Arabia needs to invest more in developing its formal recycling infrastructure, strengthen regulatory measures to ensure proper disposal of e-waste, and promote public awareness programs. Furthermore, they propose that integrating predictive models into e-waste management could provide valuable insights, helping the country better manage its growing e-waste problem while improving environmental sustainability.

2.4 Work to Be Carried Out in Light of the Literature

Based on the limitations identified in existing research, this thesis proposes a system that leverages machine learning to predict device lifespans with greater accuracy and personalization. The system will combine various device attributes, including brand, model, usage patterns, and environmental conditions, to provide a comprehensive prediction of device longevity. The review highlights the need for a system that not only predicts device lifespan but also promotes responsible e-waste management by informing users when their devices are likely to need replacement or recycling. The next steps involve building a predictive model that addresses the gaps identified in the literature, including the need for larger datasets and more personalized predictions.

CHAPTER 3: PROPOSED SYSTEM

3.1 Objectives of the Proposed System

The primary goal of this project is to create a predictive system capable of estimating the lifespan of electronic devices using machine learning models. The system will enable users to make informed decisions about device replacement, leading to reduced e-waste generation and more efficient device usage. The following objectives outline the focus areas of the proposed system:

1. **Development of a Predictive Model:** Implement a machine learning model that uses device attributes such as brand, model, usage frequency, and environmental conditions to predict the remaining lifespan of devices.
2. **User-Friendly Web Interface:** Create a simple, intuitive web interface where users can input device details (type, brand, model, usage) and receive lifespan predictions.
3. **Database for Storing Device Data:** Implement a database which stores device information that users enter which can be used for training the ml model further.

3.2 User Requirements Specification

The user requirements specify the system's functional and non-functional aspects, ensuring it meets user expectations and is robust for real-world usage.

User Input:

The system must allow users to input device details such as:

- Device type (e.g., smartphone, laptop, tablet)
 - Brand and model
 - Usage frequency (e.g., hours per day)
 - Environmental conditions (e.g., operating temperature, humidity)
 - Device condition (e.g., age, physical damage, battery health)
2. **Lifespan Prediction:** Based on the inputs provided, the system will return a prediction for the remaining lifespan of the device in terms of years.
 3. **Actionable Recommendations:**

The system will offer suggestions based on predicted lifespan, such as:

 - **Maintenance Tips:** For users whose devices have a long predicted lifespan but show signs of wear.
 - **Replacement Alerts:** For devices that are approaching their end-of-life and should be replaced or recycled.

3.3 System Architecture Overview

The architecture of the proposed system follows a modular design, ensuring maintainability and flexibility. It includes the following components:

1. **Frontend (User Interface):**
 - Built using **HTML, CSS, and JavaScript** with the **Flask** framework to create dynamic web pages.
 - User inputs device details and views predictions.
2. **Backend (Prediction Engine):**
 - **Flask** will handle HTTP requests and responses, interacting with the prediction engine to return results.
 - The prediction engine will use a machine learning model trained on a dataset of device attributes and lifespan data.
3. **Database (Storage System):**
 - **Supabase** will store device information taken in through a survey.
4. **Machine Learning Model:**
 - A predictive model trained using historical data will provide lifespan predictions.
 - The model will be continuously improved as new data is collected from users.

CHAPTER 4: ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

4.1 Flow Diagrams

Fig 1: flow diagram for prediction page

Fig 2: flow diagram for survey page

4.2 Module Specification

The system will be divided into the following modules:

1. **Data Collection Module:** Collects user input and device data.
2. **Prediction Engine:** Uses the trained machine learning model to provide lifespan predictions.
3. **Visualization Module:** Presents results to users through interactive charts and tables.
4. **User Profile Management:** Manages user data, preferences, and historical predictions.

4.3 User Interface Design

The user interface will be designed to be intuitive and user-friendly:

- **Home Page:** Allows user to pick between results page and prediction page.

- **Prediction Page:** Allows user to enter device information and get lifespan prediction.

- **Results Page:** Displays the prediction results to the user.

- **Survey Page:** Allows users to fill a survey and help improve the ML model.

CHAPTER 5: WORK DONE

The development of the website focused on device lifespan prediction and e-waste awareness involved several key stages, combining web development, machine learning, and database management to create a seamless user experience. Below is an overview of the work completed:

5.1 Frontend Development

The website was designed with a user-friendly interface to provide visitors with two clear options:

- **Predict Device Lifespan:** Redirects users to a page where they input device details (type, model, brand, type of use) and receive a prediction of their device's lifespan.
- **Fill Out Survey:** Redirects users to a page to input similar device details, along with the number of years their device lasted, contributing data for future model refinement. The frontend was developed using:
 - **HTML, CSS, and JavaScript** for a clean and responsive design.
 - Flask for routing and dynamic content rendering.

5.2 Backend Development

The backend was implemented to handle data processing and interactions between the frontend and database. Key components include:

- **Data Processing Logic:** A Flask backend was used to collect inputs from both the prediction and survey pages.
- **Prediction Model Integration:** A machine learning model (trained separately) was integrated into the backend to process user inputs from the prediction page and return a predicted lifespan.
- **Secure Data Handling:** Input data from the survey page was securely processed and stored in a PostgreSQL database hosted on Supabase.

5.3 Machine Learning Model

The prediction model was designed to estimate device lifespans based on historical data. The development of this model included:

- **Data Collection:** A dataset was prepared from information available in online forums and user-submitted survey data, focusing on device attributes like type, brand, and usage patterns.
- **Model Training:** A regression-based machine learning model was chosen for its ability to predict numeric outcomes, providing accurate lifespan estimates based on user inputs.
- **Model Evaluation:** The model was evaluated for accuracy using metrics like Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and R^2 score to ensure reliability.

5.4 Database Integration

A PostgreSQL database hosted on Supabase was set up to store survey data securely.

- **Schema Design:** Tables were created to store device information, survey data, and prediction results.
- **Data Persistence:** Only survey data (device type, brand, model, type of use, and years lasted) was saved to the database for model refinement and analysis.
- **Scalability:** The database schema was designed to accommodate future data expansions and model training requirements.

5.5 Results Display

The system was designed to present clear and actionable results to the user:

- **Results Page:** After entering device details in the prediction page, users are redirected to a results page displaying their device's predicted lifespan along with confidence levels.

5.6 Outcome

The project successfully developed a functional and user-friendly website that allows users to predict their device's lifespan or contribute valuable data through a survey. The integration of a machine learning model provided accurate lifespan predictions based on device attributes, while survey data was securely stored in a PostgreSQL database for future model refinement. Users benefited from actionable insights, helping them make informed decisions about device usage and recycling, thereby promoting e-waste awareness. The system effectively combines data-driven predictions with environmental consciousness, laying a strong foundation for future enhancements and scalability.

CHAPTER 6: LIMITATIONS, FUTURE SCOPE AND CONCLUSION

6.1 Limitations

The current implementation of the project achieves its primary objectives but leaves room for improvements that align with the proposed future scope. Below are the existing limitations of the system and how they can be addressed through the outlined future developments:

1. Limited Prediction Accuracy

- The current machine learning model relies on basic regression techniques, which may not fully capture complex relationships between device attributes and lifespan.

2. Insufficient Dataset Diversity

- The dataset used for training the model is primarily sourced from user-submitted surveys, limiting the model's ability to generalize across diverse devices and usage patterns.

3. Simplistic User Interface

- The system's current interface offers basic functionality but lacks advanced visualization tools and personalized recommendations that could improve user engagement.

4. Lack of Regional Customization

- Predictions do not account for regional differences such as climate, environmental conditions, or local device usage patterns, reducing their relevance in specific contexts.

5. Limited E-Waste Recycling Integration

- The system raises awareness about e-waste but does not provide direct integration with recycling networks or actionable recommendations for proper device disposal.

6. Scalability Concerns

- As the user base and dataset grow, the current infrastructure may face challenges in handling increased loads, potentially affecting performance.

6.2 Future Scope:

The project provides a strong foundation for device lifespan prediction and e-waste awareness, but there is significant potential for further enhancements and scalability. Below are the key areas for future development:

Integration of Advanced Machine Learning Models

- Implementing more sophisticated machine learning techniques, such as neural networks or ensemble methods, could improve prediction accuracy by capturing complex relationships between device attributes and lifespan.
- Incorporating deep learning models may also allow for handling larger datasets with more features.

Expansion of Data Sources

- Collecting data from additional sources, such as manufacturers, service centers, and e-waste recycling facilities, would improve the model's robustness and accuracy.

Enhanced User Interface

- Introducing advanced visualization tools, such as dynamic dashboards or comparative analytics, could make the system more engaging and informative for users.
- Personalized recommendations for device maintenance or recycling options could be added to improve user experience.

Geographic and Cultural Customization

- Expanding the system to support region-specific predictions by considering environmental factors such as climate, regional power fluctuations, and local usage trends.
- Developing multilingual support for broader accessibility.

Integration with Recycling Networks

- Establishing partnerships with recycling companies and providing users with direct links or suggestions for certified e-waste recycling facilities.
- Implementing a reward-based system to encourage proper disposal of end-of-life devices.

Scalability and Cloud Integration

- Migrating the prediction engine and database to a scalable cloud infrastructure could support a growing user base and handle larger datasets efficiently.
- Incorporating APIs for third-party integration, allowing manufacturers or retailers to use the prediction service.

6.3 Conclusion

The project successfully addresses the critical issue of e-waste awareness by providing a platform for predicting device lifespans and collecting valuable user data through surveys. By integrating a machine learning model with a user-friendly web interface and a robust PostgreSQL database, the system delivers actionable insights to users, helping them make informed decisions about device usage and recycling. The project's dual functionality—offering predictions and gathering survey data—creates a foundation for refining the model and contributing to the global effort to mitigate e-waste.

Despite its achievements, the project has limitations, such as reliance on static user inputs and a relatively small dataset, which highlight opportunities for future improvements. Enhancing prediction accuracy, expanding data sources, integrating real-time data, and providing stronger recycling network connections can significantly elevate the system's impact.

Overall, this project represents an important step toward combining technology and environmental awareness, demonstrating how data-driven solutions can support sustainability. With further development, it has the potential to become a comprehensive tool for device lifecycle management and e-waste reduction.

References:

1. Lenny Halim and Yosephine Suharyanti, "E-Waste: Current Research and Future Perspective on Developing Countries.", International Journal of Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management, vol. 1, no. 2, 2020, p.25.
2. M. Khurrum S. Bhutta, Adnan Omar and Xiaozhe Yang, "Electronic Waste: A Growing Concern in Today's Environment.", Economics Research International, vol. 2011, no. 1, 2011, p.8.
3. Pankaj R. Kaushik and Sunil Herat, "Current State of e-waste management in India.", International Journal of Environment and Waste Management, vol. 25, no. 3, 2020, p.322.
4. M. V Ramesh, Muthukumar Paramasivan, Akshay P. and Jarin T., "A review on electric and electronic waste material management in 21st century", Materials Today Proceedings.
5. Munam Ali Shah and Rakshandha Batool, "An Overview of Electronic Waste Management, Practices and Impending Challenges", International journal of Computer Applications, vol. 125, no. 2, p.33.
6. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/ml-linear-regression>